

ENHANCING WEB APPLICATION DETECTION AND MERGING YUBIKEY PROTOCOLS

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

The project focuses on two main areas of cyber-security at CERN:

1. **Yubikey Integration:** Examine and streamline the registration and usage of Yubikeys for Single Sign-On (SSO) and Secure Shell (SSH). The focus is on merging the existing protocols to create a unified approach for user authentication.
2. **Web Application Detection (WAD) Enhancement:** Transition the WAD tool to Python 3, integrate it with the latest CERN Single Sign-On (SSO), and improve its detection capabilities. This will provide a comprehensive view of the diverse web technologies used across various CERN projects.

ABSTRACT

CERN operates within a vast digital ecosystem that demands state-of-the-art cyber-security measures. This report underscores two projects pivotal to fortifying CERN’s digital defenses.

The imperative for Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) in safeguarding user credentials has become increasingly evident in the face of escalating cyber-security threats. While software-based MFA, encompassing OTPs, SMS, and push notifications, provides a heightened security layer compared to single-factor authentication, it is not impervious to cyber-attacks, such as phishing. Yubikeys, utilizing advanced techniques like Origin Checking, Asymmetric Cryptography, and Token Binding, protect against vulnerabilities inherent in software-based solutions. Concurrently, CERN is amplifying its cyber-security infrastructure by mandating 2FA, thereby fortifying its digital platforms against potential breaches. My work involved researching and reporting on the feasibility of integrating the two distinct protocols used in the authentication process, ultimately concluding that implementation is not viable at the current moment.

Secondly, the deployment of the Web Application Detection (WAD) tool is pivotal in monitoring the extensive technological infrastructure at CERN, especially considering the autonomy provided to teams in selecting their technology stacks. The WAD tool facilitates the early identification of vulnerabilities by providing insights into the technological landscape, thereby contributing to the fortification of web security across various platforms and applications. I have contributed upgrades to the WAD tool focusing on enhancing detection accuracy with updated Wappalyzer rules, improving usability, adapting Wappalyzer’s structural changes, and ensuring effective identification of web applications amidst new SSO system integrations.

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I am immensely grateful to CERN and CERN Openlab for presenting me with the exceptional opportunity to be a part of the Openlab Summer Student Programme. This experience has not only enhanced my technical knowledge and skills but also allowed me to be a part of a project of substantial relevance and impact.

A special acknowledgment to my fellow interns and friends, whose companionship has made this journey enjoyable and memorable. The collaborative discussions and shared experiences have enriched my internship and provided me with a global perspective that I will cherish in my future endeavours.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

.....

1	Introduction	5
2	Merging Yubikey Authentication Mechanisms	6
a.	Project Goals	6
b.	Requirements	6
c.	Results	6
d.	Conclusion	7
3	Enhancements to Web Application Detection	8
a.	Project Goals	8
b.	Requirements	9
i.	Migration to Python 3	9
ii.	Technologies and Libraries	9
iii.	Application Workflow	9
c.	Results	11
i.	Detection Capabilities	11
ii.	Challenges	11
d.	Future Work	11
i.	Contribution to Detection Rules	11
ii.	Transition to BeautifulSoup	12
iii.	Exploration of Nuclei	12
iv.	Addressing Wappalyzer’s Closed Source Status	12
e.	Conclusions	12

1 INTRODUCTION

CERN’s reputation as a leading scientific institution is matched by its commitment to maintaining a secure digital infrastructure. A pivotal aspect of this cyber-security is the implementation of robust MFA mechanisms. In my investigation into the standards employed by Yubikeys, I specifically explored the One-Time Password (OTP) legacy protocol and the Fast Identity Online 2 (FIDO2) protocol, both of which are currently utilized in different contexts within our digital environment. While OTP is required for SSH, my exploration was geared towards understanding the feasibility and implications of employing FIDO2 for SSH, with an aim to potentially eliminate the need for the legacy system, thereby enhancing the user authentication experience by converging to a singular, secure system.

Furthermore, CERN’s distinctive approach, which allows teams the autonomy to select their technological frameworks, necessitates a comprehensive system to monitor and catalog these varied choices. The Web Application Detection (WAD) tool has been instrumental in this regard. However, to navigate through the modern technological advancements and the multifaceted tech landscape at CERN, there is a compelling need to augment and modernize the WAD tool. Its role is vital in discerning the diverse technological preferences across projects, ensuring that each choice, regardless of its diversity, is in strict adherence to the highest cyber-security standards and practices.

2 MERGING YUBIKEY AUTHENTICATION MECHANISMS

A. PROJECT GOALS

As CERN is currently rolling out mandatory two-factor authentication, the objective of the project was to streamline the dual registration process of Yubikeys for 2FA. While the Single Sign-On (SSO) system, Keycloak, was equipped to handle the FIDO2 protocol, SSH relied on the older legacy OTP protocol. This resulted in the need for users to register their Yubikeys in two distinct locations: the SSO and a separate portal for SSH.

Figure 1: Yubikey registration process

B. REQUIREMENTS

In order to utilize SSH with the FIDO2 protocol, several technical specifications were identified:

- The OpenSSH version for both local and remote machines must be $\geq 8.2p1$ (for Yubikeys working in non-discoverable mode) or ≥ 8.3 (discoverable mode);
- Compilation of OpenSSH with the `-with-security-key-builtin` flag;
- Yubikey PIN initialization was mandatory;
- For Yubikey discoverable functionality, firmware version $\geq 5.1.2$ was required and $\geq 5.2.3$ for utilising the ed25519 curve.

C. RESULTS

During the exploration phase, compatibility and support issues across different operating systems were identified:

- Linux
 - Specific distributions support the required OpenSSH versions, notably RHEL 9, AlmaLinux 9, Rocky Linux 9, and CentOS 9 Stream;
 - Issues with the `ssh-sk-helper` were observed in an Alma9 VM, potentially due to incompatibilities with the `libfido2.so` version.

- MacOS
 - Apple distributes a default version of OpenSSH that is high enough but compiled without the `-with-security-key-builtin` flag, necessitating an alternative installation through Homebrew.
- Windows
 - OpenSSH version v9.2.2.0p1-Beta provided the required support, though it remains in beta;
 - Native support is absent in the most common SSH solution for Windows users, PuTTY; a fork with adequate support, PuTTY-CAC, is still under development;
 - Windows Subsystem for Linux 2 (WSL2) exhibited recognition issues with the Yubikey for FIDO2 credentials.

D. CONCLUSION

Upon evaluating the technical challenges, the project was found non-viable for immediate implementation for several reasons:

- The fragmented support across platforms and the preliminary state of required software versions posed significant implementation barriers;
- Enforcing PIN setup on Yubikeys was identified as a potential user inconvenience. While setting up a PIN adds an extra layer of security, its enforcement was ruled out due to concerns about users forgetting their PINs. Such scenarios could lead to locked accounts, increased support requests, and potential delays in work processes;
- The necessity to use a separate and not supported version of PuTTY was determined to be impractical. Requiring users to transition to a different PuTTY version would disrupt established workflows and introduce unnecessary complexities. Moreover, this would entail comprehensive user training and communication efforts.

The future potential for seamless integration remains promising. With updates and enhancements from third-party software providers, the desired consolidation of Yubikey registration could be easily achievable. However, the timeline for such updates remains uncertain, and waiting for these changes to materialize does not align with CERN's immediate objectives.

Consequently, maintaining the dual registration process, which utilizes both the OTP legacy protocol and the FIDO2 protocol, not only ensures a consistent user experience and system reliability but also strategically avoids placing all our cyber-security "eggs" in one basket. This approach mitigates risks by not being overly reliant on a single authentication protocol, thereby safeguarding against potential vulnerabilities inherent in any one system.

3 ENHANCEMENTS TO WEB APPLICATION DETECTION

A. PROJECT GOALS

The Web Application Detection (WAD) tool operates as an integral component in the ecosystem of web application identification at CERN. The tool's primary function is to identify and categorize technologies used in web applications based on distinct characteristics and markers. The enhancement goals for the WAD tool are multifaceted and are detailed as follows:

- **Detection Accuracy:** The primary focus is to enhance the detection capabilities of the WAD tool. To achieve this:
 - The tool was updated to use the latest Wappalyzer rules, ensuring that it stays up-to-date with the most recent technology signatures for accurate detection;
 - Transitioned the tool from Python 2 to Python 3, leveraging more efficient libraries such as "requests" in place of "urllib" for improved performance and accuracy.
- **Usability Improvements:** To make the WAD tool more user-friendly and efficient:
 - The command-line interface was revamped, replacing the deprecated "optparse" with "argparse" for better command-line argument handling;
 - Introduced the capability for users to output results to a specified folder, enhancing the tool's flexibility.
- **Adapting to Wappalyzer's Changes:** Recognizing the foundational role of Wappalyzer in the WAD tool's operation, alterations in Wappalyzer's dictionary structure can substantially influence detection capabilities. Therefore, actions taken include:
 - Modifying the script that downloads the regex rules to accommodate their distribution across multiple alphabetical files;
 - Adapting the parsing of technology detection rules to support list values, ensuring compatibility with the updated rules;
 - Conducting tests post-adaptation to guarantee consistent performance.
- **SSO Bypass:** In light of the recent integration of the Kerberos authentication mechanism in the Single Sign-On (SSO) system, measures have been taken to ensure the WAD tool's effectiveness. These include:
 - Utilizing the `auth-get-sso-cookie` utility, a successor to `cern-get-sso-cookie`, to procure the CERN Single Sign-On cookie using Kerberos credentials;
 - Executing rigorous tests to confirm the tool's ability to identify web applications protected by the new SSO system.

These meticulously defined goals underscore the commitment to ensuring that the WAD tool remains a robust, reliable, and indispensable asset in the realm of web application detection at CERN.

B. REQUIREMENTS

In order to refine the WAD tool, a multitude of requirements were outlined, driven by technological advancements and the evolving landscape of web application detection. This section delves into the methodologies and technologies that were employed to satiate these requisites.

i. Migration to Python 3

Given that Python 2 had already reached its end-of-life, the migration completely to Python 3 was a necessity to ensure the continued viability and compatibility of the WAD tool. This migration encompassed:

- Utilizing tools like `modernize` and `pyupgrade` to facilitate the bulk of the transition, transforming legacy syntax into its contemporary counterpart;
- Deliberate manual adjustments to rectify specific segments of the code, and to harness the enhanced features and optimizations offered by Python 3.

ii. Technologies and Libraries

The incorporation of modern Python libraries and utilities proved crucial in enhancing the tool's capabilities and optimizing the user experience:

- **Requests:** An intuitive library that has become the de facto standard for making HTTP requests in Python, it replaced the archaic `urllib` module, offering a more ergonomic interface and improved performance;
- **Argparse:** This library was integrated to provide an enhanced command-line interface, superseding the now-deprecated `optparse`;
- **Kerberos Authentication:** The inclusion of the `auth-get-sso-cookie` utility enabled the tool to adeptly navigate the Kerberos authentication layer, assuring uninterrupted access to CERN's SSO protected pages.

iii. Application Workflow

With the goal of maximizing the WAD tool's accuracy and efficiency, a revised workflow was established. This workflow is both intuitive and streamlined, ensuring users can easily adapt to the enhancements made during the project:

1. **Updating Technology Signatures:** An essential precursor to detection is ensuring the WAD tool is equipped with the most current technology signatures. By executing the `./update_technologies.py` script, users can be confident that the tool is aligned with the latest version of the regex rules from Wappalyzer. This proactive step is instrumental in achieving precise technology detection;
2. **Web Application Detection with wad-cern:** With the technology signatures updated, users can proceed to the core functionality, employing the `./wad-cern.py` script. The flexibility of this script caters to various user requirements, as detailed below:

- *Centrally Hosted Websites:* For centrally managed websites, such as CERN’s homepage, users can utilize the ‘-c’ flag combined with the ‘-n’ flag to denote the website’s name. The command `./wad-cern.py -c -n home`, for instance, is tailored specifically for scanning the CERN homepage;
- *CERN Webservers:* To inspect specific webservers within CERN, the ‘-n’ flag is all that’s needed. For example, running `./wad-cern.py -n indico` would scan the Indico webserver;
- *External URLs:* The tool remains versatile, with the capability to scrutinize any given URL. By deploying the ‘-u’ flag followed by the desired URL, users can achieve this. For batch scanning, the tool supports a file input containing a list of URLs. This is accomplished by prefixing the file path with an ‘@’ symbol.

3. **Advanced Usage Scenarios:** Beyond the basic detection capabilities, the WAD tool offers advanced functionalities to cater to specialized use cases:

- For users who wish to perform batch scans on a list of websites and direct the output to a specific directory, the combined use of the ‘-u’ flag (with a file reference) and the ‘-d’ flag achieves this purpose. `./wad-cern -u @websites_sample.txt -d scan_results`
- For scanning webpages protected by the Keycloak SSO, a keytab file with the necessary permissions is a prerequisite. Once this is set up, users can seamlessly traverse the protected pages, as demonstrated by the command `./wad-cern -krb certro -t ./certro.keytab -u https://gitlab.cern.ch/`

Figure 2: Identifying technologies on a web page using the wad-cern tool.

C. RESULTS

The updated WAD tool was evaluated on a set of 50 sites from the `websites_sample.txt` file which contains 17552 CERN hosted websites. This section outlines the key findings and challenges encountered during this evaluation.

i. Detection Capabilities

The tool exhibited proficiency in recognizing a range of web technologies:

- Webservers: Apache, IIS
- Static Site Generators: Hugo
- Web Frameworks: ASP.NET
- Operating Systems: Windows Server
- Programming Languages: PHP
- Web Proxies: Nginx

ii. Challenges

A couple of issues were noted during testing:

- A website employing the old SSO stalled the tool, as the updated tool is designed for the new SSO;
- On other sites, the tool faced a redirection loop during the SSO process, possibly due to Kerberos ticket permissions. This issue requires further investigation as I was unable to provide a working solution for it.

These observations provide insights into the tool's capabilities and potential areas for improvement.

D. FUTURE WORK

The WAD tool has undergone significant enhancements during this project, but like any evolving software, there remain avenues for future exploration and development. The following outlines potential directions for future work:

i. Contribution to Detection Rules

Given the tool's specific application within the CERN ecosystem, there's an opportunity to contribute to and refine the detection rules set, ensuring they are tailored to technologies predominantly used at CERN. This would enhance the tool's accuracy and relevance within this particular environment.

ii. Transition to BeautifulSoup

Currently, WAD relies on regex for HTML parsing. However, transitioning to a library like BeautifulSoup could offer more robust and flexible HTML parsing capabilities. This shift could enhance the tool's efficiency and accuracy in technology detection.

iii. Exploration of Nuclei

Considering the evolving landscape of technology detection and vulnerability scanning, it's worth investigating the potential of integrating or developing a new tool in Go using Nuclei. Nuclei offers a plethora of capabilities, from technology detection to vulnerability scanning, based on a simple YAML DSL. This could be explored alongside existing tools like ZAP and WAD to provide a more comprehensive detection suite.

iv. Addressing Wappalyzer's Closed Source Status

A significant challenge arose during the project's timeline when Wappalyzer, a foundational component of the WAD tool, transitioned to a closed-source model. The implications of this decision have far-reaching consequences for the WAD tool, given its heavy reliance on community-contributed regex rules. In light of this development, CERN has cloned the last publicly available repository of Wappalyzer for interim use. However, the future of the tool hinges on the direction the community takes with the existing forks of Wappalyzer. This uncertainty further underscores the importance of exploring alternative solutions, such as Nuclei, to ensure sustainable technology detection capabilities.

E. CONCLUSIONS

The enhancement of the Web Application Detector (WAD) tool during this project encapsulates a journey of modernization, adaptability, and confronting unforeseen challenges. The objective was clear: to revamp WAD for better accuracy and adapt it to CERN's evolving technical environment. Notable achievements include the successful migration from Python 2 to Python 3, the integration of modern libraries, and the adaptation to CERN's new SSO system. These accomplishments highlight the tool's renewed capability to detect a myriad of web technologies with improved efficiency. Yet, challenges were part and parcel of this endeavor. The transition of Wappalyzer to a closed-source model emphasized the unpredictability inherent in relying on external open-source tools. It underscored the significance of community collaboration in maintaining and updating technology detection rules. In retrospect, this project has not only achieved its primary goals but has also shed light on the importance of adaptability and forward-thinking in software development. The work on WAD serves as a testament to the dynamic nature of technology, emphasizing the need for tools to evolve and adapt in tandem with the environment they operate in. It sets the stage for further enhancements and exploration, ensuring that WAD remains a valuable asset in technology detection at CERN.